

INTUITIONISTIC FUZZY TOPOLOGICAL
OPERATORS AND TOPOLOGY

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Abstract: The introduction of intuitionistic fuzzy sets is due to K.T. Atanassov who, also, defined various topological operators for these sets. D. Çoker defined the intuitionistic fuzzy topological spaces. In this paper we show relations between Atanassov's topological operators and Çoker's intuitionistic fuzzy topology.

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1. Introduction

The introduction of “intuitionistic fuzzy sets” is due to K.T. Atanassov [1], and this theory has been developed in many papers [4]. This author, also defined “topological operators” over the set of IFSs, and obtained their basic properties [2, 3, 5].

On the other hand, D. Çoker defined the notion of “intuitionistic fuzzy topological spaces” [6], and he and co-workers have constructed the basic concepts of these spaces.

Atanassov, in [4] proposed as an open problem “to investigate the topological and geometric properties of the IFSs” remarking that “some first steps in this directions are made”.

In this paper we show relations between Atanassov's topological operators and Çoker's intuitionistic fuzzy topology, in particular, we give a characterization of the closure operator in Çoker's IFTSs.

First, we list the previous definitions.

Definition 1. (see [1]) Let X be a nonempty fixed set. An intuitionistic fuzzy set (IFS for short) A is an object having the form

$$A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A, \gamma_A \rangle \mid x \in X \},$$

where the functions $\mu_A : X \rightarrow I$ and $\gamma_A : X \rightarrow I$ denote the degree of membership and the degree of nonmembership of each element $x \in X$ to an ordinary subset of X , and $0 \leq \mu_A(x) + \gamma_A(x) \leq 1$ for each $x \in X$.

Definition 2. (see [2]) Let X be a nonempty set, and the IFSs A and B . Then:

- (a) $A \subseteq B$ if $\mu_A(x) \leq \mu_B(x)$ and $\gamma_A(x) \geq \gamma_B(x)$ for all $x \in X$.
- (b) $A = B$ if $A \subseteq B$ and $B \subseteq A$.
- (c) $\bar{A} = \{ \langle x, \gamma_A, \mu_A \rangle \mid x \in X \}$.
- (d) $A \cap B = \{ \langle x, \mu_A \wedge \mu_B, \gamma_A \vee \gamma_B \rangle \mid x \in X \}$.
- (e) $A \cup B = \{ \langle x, \mu_A \vee \mu_B, \gamma_A \wedge \gamma_B \rangle \mid x \in X \}$.

Definition 3. (see [6]) Let $\{A_j \mid j \in J\}$ be an arbitrary family of IFSs in X . Then

- (a) $\bigcap A_j = \{ \langle x, \bigwedge \mu_{A_j}, \bigvee \gamma_{A_j} \rangle \mid x \in X \}$.
- (b) $\bigcup A_j = \{ \langle x, \bigvee \mu_{A_j}, \bigwedge \gamma_{A_j} \rangle \mid x \in X \}$.

Definition 4. (see [6]) Let X be a nonempty set,

$$0_{\sim} = \{ \langle x, 0, 1 \rangle \mid x \in X \} \quad \text{and}$$

$$1_{\sim} = \{ \langle x, 1, 0 \rangle \mid x \in X \}.$$

Definition 5. (see [2]) Let X be a nonempty set, and A be an IFS in X . We determine for it the four numbers

$$K = \max_{x \in X} \{ \mu_A(x) \}, \quad L = \min_{x \in X} \{ \gamma_A(x) \},$$

$$k = \min_{x \in X} \{ \mu_A(x) \}, \quad l = \min_{x \in X} \{ \gamma_A(x) \},$$

and the IFS

$$C(A) = \{ \langle x, K, L \rangle \mid x \in X \},$$

$$I(A) = \{ \langle x, k, l \rangle \mid x \in X \}$$

called closure and interior of A .

Atanassov [1] proves that, for every IFSs A and B :

- (a) $I(A) \subseteq A \subseteq C(A)$.
- (b) $C(A \cup B) = C(A) \cup C(B)$.
- (c) $C(C(A)) = C(A)$.
- (d) $C(0_\sim) = 0_\sim$.
- (e) $I(\overline{A}) = C(A)$.

Definition 6. (see [6]) An intuitionistic fuzzy topology (IFT for short) on a nonempty set X is a family τ of IFSs in X satisfying the following axioms:

- (1) $0_\sim, 1_\sim \in \tau$.
- (2) $G_1 \cap G_2 \in \tau$ for any $G_1, G_2 \in \tau$.
- (3) $\cup G_j \in \tau$ for any arbitrary family $\{G_j | j \in J\} \subset \tau$.

In this case the pair (X, τ) is called an intuitionistic fuzzy topological space (IFTS for short), any IFS in τ is said an intuitionistic fuzzy open set (IFOS for short) in X , and the complement of an IFOS is called an intuitionistic fuzzy closed set (IFCS for short) in X .

Theorem 1. Let X be a non-empty set, \mathcal{S} the family of all IFSs in X , and the mapping

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi : \mathcal{S} &\rightarrow \mathcal{S}, \\ A &\rightarrow C(A). \end{aligned}$$

If we denote $\mathcal{F} = \{F \text{ IFS} | C(F) = F\}$, then $\tau = \{\overline{F} | F \in \mathcal{F}\}$ is an IFT on X in the Çoker's sense.

Proof. First note that, if A, B are IFSs with $A \subseteq B$ then $C(A) \subseteq C(B)$.

Now suppose $\{F_j\}_{j \in J} \subset \mathcal{F}$. Then, since $\bigcap_{j \in J} F_j \subseteq F_{j_0}$ for each $j_0 \in J$,

we have that $C\left(\bigcap_{j \in J} F_j\right) \subseteq C(F_{j_0})$ for each $j_0 \in J$ and $C\left(\bigcap_{j \in J} F_j\right) \subseteq$

$\bigcap_{j \in J} C(F_j) = \bigcap_{j \in J} F_j$. The reverse inclusion is also true, so $C\left(\bigcap_{j \in J} F_j\right) = \bigcap_{j \in J} F_j$,

that is $\bigcap_{j \in J} F_j \in \mathcal{F}$.

If $F_1, F_2 \in \mathcal{F}$, $C(F_1 \cup F_2) = C(F_1) \cup C(F_2) = F_1 \cup F_2$ so $F_1 \cup F_2 \in \mathcal{F}$.

Finally $C(0_\sim) = 0_\sim$ and $C(1_\sim) = 1_\sim$ give that $0_\sim, 1_\sim$ belongs to \mathcal{F} .

Thus $\tau = \{\overline{F} | F \in \mathcal{F}\}$ is IFT on X , by De Morgan's laws. \square

Remark 1. The closure operator of Atanassov defines a Çoker's intuitionistic fuzzy topology, but if we take a IFTS the closures of IFS of it in the

Atanassov's sense are not necessarily IFCSs in the IFTS. Indeed: Let $X = I$, the unit interval, $\mu : I \rightarrow I$ the map such that $\mu(x) = \frac{x}{2} + \frac{1}{4}$, and $A = \langle x, \mu, \mu' \rangle$. If $\tau = \{0_{\sim}, 1_{\sim}, A\}$ we have that (I, τ) is IFTS. The family of all IFCSs in (I, τ) is $\{1_{\sim}, 0_{\sim}, \bar{A}\}$, thus, the closure of A in the Atanassov's sense $C(A)$ is not IFCS in (I, τ) :

$$C(A) = \langle x, K, L \rangle \quad \text{such that}$$

$$K = \max\{\mu(x) | x \in I\} = \frac{3}{4},$$

$$L = \min\{\mu'(x) | x \in I\} = \frac{1}{4} \quad (\mu'(x) = \frac{3}{4} - \frac{x}{2}).$$

D. Çoker defined in IFTS other operators.

Definition 7. (see [6]) Let (X, τ) be an IFTS and A be an IFS in X .

$$\text{cl}(A) = \bigcap_{\substack{F \text{ IFCS} \\ A \subseteq F}} F, \quad \text{int}(A) = \bigcup_{\substack{F \text{ IFOS} \\ G \subseteq A}} G$$

Remark 2. D. Çoker [6] proves that:

- (a) $\text{cl}(A)$ is an IFCS.
- (b) $A \subseteq \text{cl}(A)$.
- (c) $\text{cl}(A) = A$ iff A is an IFCS.
- (d) $\text{cl}(\text{cl}(A)) = \text{cl}(A)$.
- (e) $\text{cl}(0_{\sim}) = 0_{\sim}$.
- (f) $\text{cl}(A \cup B) = \text{cl}(A) \cup \text{cl}(B)$.

We will use these properties of Çoker's closure for give a characterization of the closure operator in IFTSs.

Theorem 2. Let X be a non-empty set, \mathcal{S} the family of all IFSs in X , and $\psi : \mathcal{S} \rightarrow \mathcal{S}$ be a mapping which verify:

- (1) $A \subseteq \psi(A)$.
- (2) $\psi(\psi(A)) = \psi(A)$.
- (3) $\psi(0_{\sim}) = 0_{\sim}$.
- (4) $\psi(A \cup B) = \psi(A) \cup \psi(B)$.

Then, if $\mathcal{F} = \{F \text{ IFS} | \psi(F) = F\}$ and $\tau = \{\bar{F} | F \in \mathcal{F}\}$, we have that τ is an IFT on X in the Çoker's sense, and, for every IFS A in X , $\psi(A)$ is the closure of A in (X, τ) .

Proof. Firstly, if A, B are IFSs with $A \subseteq B$ then $\psi(A) \subseteq \psi(B)$ by (4).

Now, suppose $\{F_j\}_{j \in J} \subset \mathcal{F}$. Then, since $\bigcap_{j \in J} F_j \subseteq F_{j_0}$ for each $j_0 \in J$, we

have that $\psi\left(\bigcap_{j \in j} F_j\right) \subseteq \psi(F_{j_0})$ for each $j_0 \in J$, and $\psi\left(\bigcap_{j \in j} F_j\right) \subseteq \bigcap_{j \in j} \psi(F_j) = \bigcap_{j \in j} F_j$. The reverse inclusion is also true, so

$$\psi\left(\bigcap_{j \in j} F_j\right) = \bigcap_{j \in j} F_j, \text{ that is } \bigcap_{j \in j} F_j \in \mathcal{F}.$$

If $F_1, F_2 \in \mathcal{F}$, $\psi(F_1 \cup F_2) = \psi(F_1) \cup \psi(F_2) = F_1 \cup F_2$, so $F_1 \cup F_2 \in \mathcal{F}$.

Finally $\psi(0_\sim) = 0_\sim$ by (3), and $\psi(1_\sim) = 1_\sim$ by (1), thus $0_\sim, 1_\sim$ belong to \mathcal{F} , and $\tau = \{\overline{F} | F \in \mathcal{F}\}$ is IFT on X .

Let A be any IFS of X . We will prove that $\psi(A)$ is the closure of A in (X, τ) . Indeed, $\psi(A)$ is IFCS in X , $A \subseteq \psi(A)$ and for every K IFCS in X such that $A \subseteq K$, we have that $\psi(A) \subseteq \psi(K) = K$ by (1) and $K \in \mathcal{F}$. \square

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